

COST OPTIMIZATION FOR DESIGNING SUSTAINABLE, INTELLIGENT AND INCLUSIVE BUILDINGS USING TRIZ

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Abstract

Purpose – To formulate a methodology for handling qualitative optimization of buildings when several target-functions are considered, such as smartness, green design and inclusiveness.

Methodology/approach - Concurrent Multi-Function Deployment method is used to study a multitude of criteria that give the performance of a building. Performance criteria such as costs, health and comfort of the inhabitants are weighted. They are in relation with target functions, such as sustainability, intelligence and inclusivity. TRIZ is included to solve several conflicts in relation with these target functions.

Findings – It is possible to formulate a balanced solution in designing a building where several target functions, such as sustainability, inclusiveness and intelligence, are taken into account.

Research limitations/implications – The methodology was tested only on three target functions and on a relatively simple building. We do not have yet a clear understanding about its reliability on complex civil engineering projects, where the entropy is very high.

Practical implications – The proposed methodology is applicable in any civil engineering project, where we need to tackle design from multiple angles.

Originality/value – Originality is defined both in terms of the methodology we have proposed to solve the design problem and in its domain of applicability. Usually, qualitative optimization of buildings has been reduced to one or maximum two target functions (e.g. inclusiveness, smartness, sustainability or a mix of two of them). By our knowledge, there is no treatment of design from an aggregated perspective of all three dimensions.

Key words: sustainability, intelligent house, cost management.

Introduction

A need has developed since the 20th century to create buildings that can function to its full potential for the purpose for which they were created. New technologies with a decisive role in their sustainability, aesthetics, efficiency, accessibility and health but also in cost reduction have been implemented in these buildings (Building Regulations, 2010).

In the approach to the design and construction of buildings as a whole, the concept of high-performance building has been introduced and must include features such as: accessibility, aesthetics, cost efficiency, functionality, productivity, inhabitants' health, safety and security, sustainability (enil.eu, 2020).

Figure 1 illustrates the characteristics of a sustainable, intelligent and inclusive building: advanced engineering, low cost, safe, competitive, open, practical, elegant and high-security building.

Figure 1. Sustainable, intelligent and inclusive building with high performance - characteristics

At the point when we talk about sustainability, we consider various qualities and materials that a structure must have. These incorporate (FOBRP,2020): recyclable materials from which the building is built and recyclable furniture, economical household appliances, economical electrical equipment, water purification system etc.

When stating that a building is intelligent, there are certain elements to be considered: flexible design, energy efficient design, Wi-Fi networks, VOIP net-works (voice over internet protocol), video monitoring, building access monitoring, automatic fire suppression, built-in support (for lighting, signaling, smoke control, etc.), integration of all building systems, energy management systems, thermal water and energy monitoring etc. (Edgar, 2016).

An inclusive building has certain features: wide doors access roads, spacious toilets, supporting railings, good natural lighting, the use of eye-pleasing colors with a guiding role inside the building, vertical traffic with ramps or elevators, communication systems, emergency exits accessible to all, fire alarms, inclusive furniture etc.

Methodology and testing

Concurrent Multi-Function Deployment (CMFD) was adopted for multi-criteria performance planning (Brad,2009). This method permits the synchronous approach of multiple objective functions and the inclusion of structured innovation in the design process of the solution. The CMFD algorithm must have a certain sequence (Brad, 2009): define the objective set of functions, identify and classify requirements related to the objective and business functions in general, analyze the objective functions in relation to the investment plans, determine and classify the value characteristics that define each objective function, generate local solutions for the entire system, plan and generate a solution by innovating and aggregating, compare the general solution to the value characteristics, define the parts that form the whole solution, execute the plan.

Figure 2. CMFD - route and associated methods

For testing the method, objective functions of a sustainable, intelligent and inclusive building (FO) and their requirement-functions (FR) were decided upon by the client/owner of the house: FO = {sustainability, intelligence, inclusiveness}, FR = {costs, health and comfort of the inhabitants}. His perspective is that the initial investment will need a maximum of 130,000 euros (FR1) with an importance of I = 25 percent, the maximum total investment cost will be 400,000 euros (FR2) with an importance I = 25 percent, the house's floors will have a surface of maximum 250 m² (FR3) with an importance I = 10 percent, the ease of operation (FR4) has an importance I = 10 percent, health protection of the inhabitants (FR5) has an importance I = 15 percent, and the protection of the environment (FR6) has an importance I = 15 percent.

Table 1. Objects / materials / equipment of objective functions

Objective function	Code	Objects / materials / equipment that meet the objective	Importance percentage (%)
Sustainability	OP ₁₁	Do not pollute the environment	G ₁₁ =9%
	OP ₁₂	Have low energy costs	G ₁₂ =23%
	OP ₁₃	Use as little water as possible	G ₁₃ =20%
	OP ₁₄	No major repairs are needed	G ₁₄ =10%
	OP ₁₅	Recyclable building materials	G ₁₅ =17%
	OP ₁₆	Furniture made of recyclable materials	G ₁₆ =5%
	OP ₁₇	To protect the health of the inhabitants	G ₁₇ =16%
Intelligence	OP ₂₁	Windows open / close automatically	G ₂₁ =11%
	OP ₂₂	The blinds open / close automatically	G ₂₂ =11%
	OP ₂₃	The front door opens / closes automatically	G ₂₃ =7%
	OP ₂₄	Heating monitoring system	G ₂₄ =20%
	OP ₂₅	Light monitoring system	G ₂₅ =19%
	OP ₂₆	Danger warning alarm	G ₂₆ =9%
	OP ₂₇	The light turns on / off automatically	G ₂₇ =7%
	OP ₂₈	Integrated audio system	G ₂₈ =4%
	OP ₂₉	Building security and protection system	G ₂₉ =12%
Inclusivity	OP ₃₁	Large rooms	G ₃₁ =13%
	OP ₃₂	Large hallways	G ₃₂ =13%
	OP ₃₃	Large bathrooms	G ₃₃ =13%
	OP ₃₄	Non-slippery floor	G ₃₄ =12%
	OP ₃₅	Lights open easily	G ₃₅ =7%
	OP ₃₆	Doors open easily	G ₃₆ =9%
	OP ₃₇	No level differences	G ₃₇ =4%
	OP ₃₈	Easily accessible alarm system	G ₃₈ =12%
	OP ₃₉	Warning signs	G ₃₉ =10%
	OP ₃₁₀	Well-lit rooms	G ₃₁₀ =7%

Table 1 reveals that sustainability has the highest importance, of 45.12 percent, followed by intelligence with 31.71 percent and inclusiveness with 23.17 percent. The value characteristics related to sustainability, inclusivity and intelligence are displayed in table 2.

Table 2. Objective function planning

Sustainability				
Intelligence				+
Inclusivity			+	-
Optimization trends		↑	↑	↑
Links: ● powerful link ⊙ medium link ⊕ possible link + positive correlation - negative correlation ↑ positive trend ↓ negative trend	Importance	Inclusivity	Intelligence	Sustainability
Initial investment max 130.000 euro	25%	⊕	●	●
Total investment max 400.000 euro	25%	⊕	●	●
House floors max 250 m ²	10%	●	⊕	⊕
Easy to operate	10%	●	⊙	⊕
Protects residents' health	15%	●	⊕	●
Protects the environment	15%	⊕	⊕	●
Value share (PV)		23.17%	31.71%	45.12%

After applying the CMFD method, a hybridization of the three concepts follows. Based on the algorithm and data, the first two buildings are merged - the sustainable building and the smart building - a hybrid building is emerging.

The designed hybrid building in Figure 3 has the following features: is covered with 15 cm thermal insulation made of recyclable materials, the windows' glass reflects sunlight, it has a ventilation and air purification plant doubled by natural ventilation, the house's heating is done with a geothermal pump, there are solar panels on the roof of the terrace, the windows have a system of embedded blinds. Furthermore, this house can be controlled remotely in terms of: heating, lighting, safety, monitoring, energy and water consumption.

Considering the relative weight of each subcomponent in association with the degree of importance of each objective function: sustainability, intelligence and inclusion, windows have the highest value of 15.29 percent, doors of 12.37 percent and HVAC monitoring system of 9.96 percent. The light monitoring system has a percentage of 8.01 percent, the walls of 7.95 percent, the thermal power supply system of 6.97 percent, the danger monitoring/warning system of 6.22 percent, the furniture of 6 .03 percent and the building surveillance system of 5.78 percent. At the end of the ranking one can find: vertical circulation with 1.91 percent, bathroom with 1.68 percent and water supply system with 1.27 percent.

Afterwards, the hybrid solution fuses with the inclusive building. When fusing, a series of conflicts appear, as seen in Figure 4. TRIZ methodology was used, a method based on logical deductions following the analysis of existing information in order to resolve these conflicts (Brad et al, 2006), (Russo and Carrara, 2019).

Figure 3. Hybrid building

For solving the first conflict: “widest possible access routes” versus “the smallest possible surface for exposing the exterior walls”, in TRIZ we have found the following generic parameters: “surface of stationary objects” and “energy loss”. Hence, the following inventive principles result for solving the problem: 1. The nest-in-nest principle, 2. The transfer principle in another dimension (multi-level arrangement, object reorientation, moving to 3D spaces) and 3. The principle of flexible walls or thin walls (innovation in the structure of the walls). In this case, of the three, the nest-in-nest principle was chosen. All rooms will be structured around a central hall, inhabitants will enter these rooms through it. A large exposure area of the exterior walls is therefore avoided.

For the second conflict: “as easy as possible access to any point in the building” and “as little footprint as possible” the following generic TRIZ parameters were selected: “surface of stationary objects” and “convenience in use”. Using TRIZ for solving this conflict, the proposed principles are: 1. The principle of partial or excessive actions and 2. The principle of asymmetry (building the building on two levels, but asymmetric). A combination of the two principles was chosen: the principle of asymmetry and the principle of “excessive actions”. The upper floor has a smaller surface than the ground floor, ensuring the regulations for buildings used by persons with disabilities. A platform hydraulic lift was also placed, ensuring the access of all residents of the building to the upper floor. The costs with this platform lift are much lower than what would have been the costs of foundations and earthworks if the building would have been constructed on a single level.

Figure 4. Inclusive building vs. hybrid building – emerging conflicts

Coveting to have the widest possible access routes and a volume of air that must be thermally controlled as small as possible, is at the basis of the third conflict. TRIZ method, identifies a series of parameters: “convenience in use” and “volume of a stationary object”. These inventive principles were brought about by TRIZ: 1. The principle of asymmetry (when heating / cooling spaces), 2. The principle of “mechanical” vibration (elevator or other easier access to the upper level), 3. The principle of use of porous materials (facilitating the movement of people inside the building) and 4. The principle of inert media (incorporation of vacuum tubes to heat several rooms). The principle of asymmetry in space heating/cooling was decided upon: both the heating and ventilation system is operated by residents on a certain daily schedule, duplicated with an intelligent system that functions when spontaneously using rooms, outside the pre-set schedule.

A large surface area of the windows and a low energy consumption is the fourth conflict, with the following TRIZ parameters: “the surface of a stationary object” and “energy loss”. The principles offered by TRIZ for solving the conflict are: 1. The nest-in-nest principle, 2. The transfer principle in another dimension (multi-level arrangement, object reorientation, moving to 3D spaces) and 3. The flexible materials principle or the thin materials principle. Using the the object reorientation principle, transfer of indoor and outdoor heat energy is aided by the automatically operated roller system. The blinds are automatically lowered if natural light is in excess and the room does not require natural lighting.

The desire to have the widest possible access routes (high mobility) and the lowest possible material consumption is what inflicted the last conflict. “Moves inside a stationary object” and “amount of material” are the parameters chosen by TRIZ with solving principles as follows: 1. The principle of local quality (choice of differentiated materials for different spaces), 2. The principle of changing parameters and 3. The principle of composite materials (use of recyclable materials, waste, etc.). Recycled materials are utilized when building: recycled brick, recycled wood, thermal system made of recyclable material, recycled parquet, furniture made of recycled materials, etc., thus using the principle of composite materials.

As a result of all the information mentioned above, the sustainable, intelligent and inclusive building was designed, as seen in figure 5.

Figure 5. Sustainable, intelligent and inclusive building

This house was developed on two floors, the ground floor 50 percent larger than the first floor, coated with 15 cm thermal insulation made of recyclable materials, exterior finishes made of recycled brick from demolition and recycled and treated plywood, cooling floor heating done with a geothermal pump. Hot water is produced with a bivalent boiler, solar panels exist on the roof's terrace. The windows have masked roller shutters with automatic operation from a switch/telephone. The house is remotely controlled regarding: heating, lighting, safety, monitoring, energy, lighting and water consumption. The building has accessible sized flows, access ramps to the main entrance and on the terrace, warning signs at the beginning and end of the ramps, the main ramp is covered and has non-slippery floors, halls and rooms allow the simultaneous passage of two wheelchairs, switches and sockets are accessible by persons in wheelchairs.

Figure 6. Initial material costs for the 5 types of buildings

Figure 6 exemplifies the initial costs for the 5 variants of houses, houses with approximately equal surfaces, of 250 m². Of these, the most expensive is the inclusive building, followed by the smart one. The cheapest building is the sustainable one, while the sustainable, smart and inclusive building is in the middle of the ranking.

Figure 7. Total costs for the 5 types of buildings

Figure 7 compares the total costs over a period of 50 years (the entire life of a construction). The comparison makes sense because all 5 buildings are variants of the same building, desired by the same beneficiary, a building with an area of about 250 m², with a predetermined initial and final budget. After analyzing the figure, we notice that the cheapest of them is the sustainable building, followed by the sustainable and intelligent one. In the middle of the ranking is the sustainable, intelligent and inclusive building. The most expensive of the buildings is the inclusive one.

Conclusions

In the sense of global developments in seeking sustainable approaches to energy and climate problems, as well as to more inclusive societies, this work offers insights into how building construction issues can be addressed.

This paper attempts to formulate a framework for managing qualitative building optimization while considering multiple goal functions, such as smartness, green design and inclusiveness.

This paper shows that a holistic approach can be designed when designing a building that takes into account several target functions, such as sustainability, inclusiveness and smartness. The approach proposed is applicable to any civil engineering project where we have to tackle design from several angles.

The drawback of this analysis, however, is that the methodology was only tested on three target functions and on a fairly simple design. On complex civil engineering ventures, where entropy is very high, we do not yet have a good understanding of its reliability. Our future efforts will be channeled into this deficiency.

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